

PREPSOIL WP5 - T.5.4. Capacity building for improved monitoring knowledge base

DRAFT PROGRAMME FOR PILOT TRAININGS ON SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS AND THE CURRENT REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

GENERAL OBJECTIVE OF THE PROGRAM

The main objective of the program is to train public officials who manage or will manage soil health data under a unified reporting system, policymakers who make decisions based on these indicators, and members of Living Labs who drive innovation and co-creation of solutions, by providing a comprehensive understanding of soil health indicators and their application within a continuously evolving regulatory and technical framework.

Participants will aim to:

- Develop an in-depth knowledge of soil functions and their role in environmental, food, and climate sustainability.
- Understand the complexity and challenges associated with defining, measuring, and applying indicators, particularly in diverse contexts such as geographic regions and specific land uses.
- Critically analyze the advances and limitations of the **Soil Monitoring Law (SML)** and the **Mission Soil initiatives**, promoting flexible and adaptive approaches that address local needs while maintaining harmonized European-level objectives.
- Acquire practical tools to implement monitoring strategies and formulate public policies based on scientific evidence and robust data.

This program combines theoretical and practical training to empower policymakers to make informed decisions, considering both the opportunities and challenges faced by soil management in Europe and globally.

DETAILED PROGRAMME

MODULE 1: FOUNDATIONS AND GLOBAL CONTEXT

Presentation 1: Soil Health in the 21st Century

Objective: Establish a conceptual framework on the importance of soil and the global challenges associated with its management.

Contents:

- **Functions and ecosystem services of soil:** Ecosystem services according to FAO: supply of food, fibers, and fuels. Habitat for organisms. Flood regulation. Source of pharmaceuticals and

genetic resources. Basis for human infrastructure. Supply of construction materials. Cultural heritage. Carbon retention. Water purification and reduction of soil contaminants. Climate regulation. Nutrient cycling.

- **Main global threats:** Erosion, compaction, acidification, contamination, sealing, salinization, waterlogging, nutrient imbalance (deficiency or excess), and loss of organic carbon and biodiversity.
- **Emerging challenges:** climate change, emerging pollutants (e.g., PFAS, microplastics).
- **Global perspective:** United Nations initiatives: Sustainable Development Goals, FAO, and IPCC.
- **European perspective:** EU initiatives, including the Soil Monitoring Law (SML), Mission Soil, "Farm to Fork" Strategy, EU Soil Strategy for 2030, Biodiversity Strategy, Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture, and Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation.
 - **SML:**
 - Main objectives, structure, and proposal of key indicators.
 - Concerns raised by Member States: Harmonization vs. local flexibility. Integration of the directive with existing national initiatives. Sampling strategies. The use of a single threshold to define healthy/unhealthy soils. Definition of different health levels.
 - **Mission Soil:**
 - Living Labs and Lighthouses as experimental and demonstrative environments.
 - Applied technological tools: Remote sensing, GIS, digital platforms.
 - Normative and technical impact: Connection between SML, Mission Soil, and local needs.

Group Debate: What local challenges do soils face in your regions? Example: Soil artificialization.

MODULE 2: KEY INDICATORS AND THEIR COMPLEXITY

[Presentation 2: Key Indicators and Their Complexity](#)

Objective: Understand the scientific and technical basis behind soil health indicators and the challenges in their application.

Contents:

- **Physical indicators:** Bulk density, structural stability, water retention capacity, erosion rate, porosity, depth of topsoil horizon, infiltration and runoff, penetration resistance, among others.
- **Chemical indicators:** Soil Organic Carbon (SOC), salinity, pH, contamination, nutrients, cation exchange capacity, exchangeable cations, and others.
- **Biological indicators:** Microbial biodiversity, basal respiration, enzymatic activity.
- **Detailed study of the indicators proposed in the SML:**

- SOC, biodiversity, bulk density, sealing, erosion, salinity and contamination, nutrient excess, subsoil compaction, reduction of soil water retention capacity, acidification, arable layer compaction, soil biodiversity loss, land occupation, and sealing.
- Analysis of their relevance and applicability in different contexts and types of land use. Uncertainty/precision of the indicators.
- Evaluation of how harmonized thresholds may influence national and regional policies.
- **The need for flexible approaches that consider regional particularities and land uses.** Emphasizing a holistic vision to address problems (avoiding the unintended exacerbation of other issues while trying to control a specific one). For example, carbon content can be increased by adding more nitrogen, but this may lead to eutrophication or GHG emissions.
- **Directed questions:** Which indicators are most relevant in specific contexts?

MODULE 3: MONITORING METHODS AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES

Presentation 3: Monitoring Methods

Objective: Explain how to conduct soil health indicator monitoring, from planning to implementation, ensuring representativeness and accuracy.

Contents:

- **Basic principles for indicator monitoring:**
 - Clear objective definition according to local and regional contexts.
 - Identification of key indicators to monitor (SOC, biodiversity, salinity, among others). **It may be necessary to distinguish between indicators that are relevant to measure in all soils (e.g., SOC, structural stability, biodiversity, etc.) and indicators that are only relevant to measure in certain contexts (salinity, certain types of contamination, etc.).**
- **Designing representative monitoring plans:**
 - Selection of sampling points based on degradation risks and spatial representativeness.
 - Monitoring frequency to ensure updated data.
- **Practical methods for data collection:**
 - Manual and traditional procedures adapted to different contexts.
 - Integration of adaptive approaches based on soil type (agricultural, forest, urban, mixed).
- **Preparation of a basic monitoring plan adapted to a case study.**

Presentation 4: Digital Technologies for Monitoring and Data Analysis

Objective: Provide participants with information on digital and technological tools needed to monitor and analyze soil health indicators accurately and efficiently.

Contents:

- **Using the digital soil health data portal:**
 - Training on access and use of digital platforms for soil data management.
- **Integration of georeferenced data and its use in indicator monitoring:**
 - Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to manage and analyze spatial data.
- **Advanced technologies as support:**
 - Remote sensing for capturing high-resolution data and integrating it into digital platforms.
 - In-situ sensors connected to digital systems for continuous monitoring of chemical and biological indicators.
- **Accessing and using large spatial databases:**
 - Developing skills to access, analyze, and utilize spatial databases in the context of soil monitoring.
- **Relation to Article 23a, Point 4 of the SML:** Determination of values for indicators such as sealing and soil destruction through digital integration.

MODULE 4: INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS AND DECISION-MAKING

Presentation 5: Indicator Evaluation and Report Preparation

Objective: Train participants in the critical interpretation of data and effective communication of results. Explore how to integrate results into the formulation of effective public policies.

Contents:

- **Evaluation of scenarios and analysis of the impact of different land management strategies** (agricultural practices, forestry, etc.), with application of models for evidence-based decision-making.
- **Comparative interpretation:** Normative thresholds and local adaptations.
- **Success examples in the implementation of soil policies based on data.**